

4-SHO‘BA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA

IKKI O‘ZGARUVCHILI FUNKSIYA UCHUN GONCHAR MASALASI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ikki o‘zgaruvchili funksiya uchun Gonchar masalasi qo‘yilgan. Ikki o‘zgaruvchili funksiya uzluksizlik moduli orqali ba‘zi funksiyalar sinfi qanday ifodalanishi ko‘rsatilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: ikki o‘zgaruvchili funksiya uzluksizlik moduli, ikki o‘zgaruvchili funksiyaning lokal uzluksizlik moduli, nuqtaning η – atrofi, ikki karrali maxsus integral.

Ma’lumki bir o‘zgaruvchili funksiya uchun uzluksizlik moduli quyidagicha kiritiladi:

Ta’rif. $\omega: R_+ \rightarrow R_+$ funksiya uzluksizlik moduli deyiladi, agar,

1) $\omega \uparrow$; 2) $\forall x_1, x_2$ uchun $\omega(x_1 + x_2) \leq \omega(x_1) + \omega(x_2)$;

3)

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \omega(x) = 0$$

bo‘lsa.

Uzluksizlik modullar to‘plamini UM orqali belgilaymiz.

$\varphi: (0, d] \cap R_+ \rightarrow R_+$, $d \in (0, d]$ funksiya yuqoridagi ta’rifning 1), 3)

shartlarini hamda 2’) $\frac{\varphi(x)}{x} \downarrow$ shartni qanoatlantirsa, u holda bunday funksiyalar sinfini

$\phi_{(0,d]}$ orqali belgilaymiz. $\phi \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \phi_{(0,+\infty]}$.

Faraz qilaylik, $\varphi \in \phi$, $x_1, x_2 \in R_+$, u holda

$$\varphi(x_1 + x_2) = \frac{x_1 \varphi(x_1 + x_2)}{x_1 + x_2} + \frac{x_2 \varphi(x_1 + x_2)}{x_1 + x_2} \leq \varphi(x_1) + \varphi(x_2),$$

ya’ni $\varphi \in UM$. Demak $\phi \subset UM$.

L_1 va L_2 egri chiziqlarning dekart ko‘paytmasidan hosil b‘lgan L torda aniqlangan $\varphi(t, \tau)$ fuksiya berilgan. Quyidagi ayirmalarni qaraymiz:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} &\varphi(\tau_1, \tau_2) - \varphi(t_1, t_2) \\ &\varphi(\tau_1, t_2) - \varphi(t_1, t_2) \\ &\varphi(t_1, \tau_2) - \varphi(t_1, t_2) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (1)$$

Quyidagi belgilashlarni kiritamiz:

$$\omega_{\varphi}^{t_0}(\delta_1, \delta_2; \eta_1, \eta_2) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \sup_{\substack{|\tau_1 - t_1| < \delta_1 \\ |\tau_2 - t_2| < \delta_2}} |\varphi(\tau_1, \tau_2) - \varphi(t_1, t_2)| \quad (2)$$

bu yerda

$$L_{\eta_1}(t_0) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{\tau_1, t_1 \in L_1: |\tau_1 - t_1| < \eta_1\},$$

$$L_{\eta_2}(t_0) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{\tau_2, t_2 \in L_2: |\tau_2 - t_2| < \eta_2\}.$$

(2) ni $\varphi(t, \tau)$ funksiyaning $t_0 \in L$ nuqtadagi lokal uzluksizlik moduli deb ataymiz.

$$\omega_{\varphi}^{t_0}(\delta_1; \eta_1) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \sup_{\substack{|\tau_1 - t_1| < \delta_1 \\ \tau_1, t_1 \in L_{\eta_1}(t_0)}} |\varphi(\tau_1, t_2) - \varphi(t_1, t_2)| \quad (3)$$

$$\omega_{\varphi}^{t_0}(\delta_2; \eta_2) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \sup_{\substack{|\tau_2 - t_2| < \delta_2 \\ \tau_2, t_2 \in L_{\eta_2}(t_0)}} |\varphi(t_1, \tau_2) - \varphi(t_1, t_2)| \quad (4)$$

(3) va (4) larni $\varphi(t, \tau)$ funksiyaning $t_0 \in L$ nuqtadagi aralash (yoki ajralgan) lokal uzluksizlik moduli deb ataymiz. (7) ni quyidagicha yozib olamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi(\tau_1, \tau_2) - \varphi(t_1, t_2) &= \varphi_1 + \varphi_2 + \varphi_{12} = \varphi(\tau_1, t_2) - \varphi(t_1, t_2) + \\ &+ \varphi(t_1, \tau_2) - \varphi(t_1, t_2) + \varphi(\tau_1, \tau_2) - \varphi(\tau_1, t_2) - \varphi(t_1, \tau_2) + \varphi(t_1, t_2) = \\ &= \varphi(\tau_1, t_2) - \varphi(t_1, t_2) + \varphi(\tau_1, \tau_2) - \varphi(\tau_1, t_2). \end{aligned}$$

Buni e'tiborga olsak, unda quyidagiga ega bo'lamiz:

$$\omega_{\varphi}^{t_0}(\delta_1, \delta_2; \eta_1, \eta_2) \leq \omega_{\varphi}^{t_0}(\delta_1; \eta_1) + \omega_{\varphi}^{t_0}(\delta_2; \eta_2) \quad (5)$$

Ikki o'zgaruvchili funksiyaning uzluksizlik moduli haqidagi masalalar ([2], [3], [4]) larda qaralgan.

Osongina ko'rish mumkiinki, $\omega_{\varphi}^{t_0}(\delta_1, \delta_2; \eta_1, \eta_2)$ funksiya quyidagi xossalarga ega:

1. $\omega_{\varphi}^{t_0}(\delta_1, \delta_2; \eta_1, \eta_2) \geq 0$ bo'lib va δ_1, δ_2 lar bir-biriga bog'liqsiz ravishda nolga intilganda $\omega_{\varphi}^{t_0}(\delta_1, \delta_2; \eta_1, \eta_2)$ nolga intiladi;

2. $\omega_{\varphi}^{t_0}(\delta_1, \delta_2; \eta_1, \eta_2)$ funksiya har bir $\delta_1, \delta_2; \eta_1, \eta_2$ argumentlari bo'yicha kamaymovchi funksiya;

3. $\frac{\omega_{\varphi}^{t_0}(\delta_1, \delta_2; \eta_1, \eta_2)}{\delta_1 \cdot \delta_2}$ funksiya har bir δ_1, δ_2 argumentlari bo'yicha o'suvchi funksiya.

Bu xossalarni e'tiborga olgan holda quyidagi ta'rifni kiritamiz.

1-ta'rif. Har bir argumenti R_+ da aniqlanib, quyidagi shartlarni qanoatlantirgan $\varphi(\delta_1, \delta_2; \eta_1, \eta_2)$ funksiyalar to'plamini Q bilan belgilaymiz:

1. $\varphi(\delta_1, \delta_2; \eta_1, \eta_2)$ har bir argumentlari bo'yicha kamaymovchi;

2. $\frac{\varphi(\delta_1, \delta_2; \eta_1, \eta_2)}{\delta_1 \cdot \delta_2}$ funksiya har bir δ_1, δ_2 argumentlari bo'yicha o'suvchi;

3. $\exists \eta_1, \eta_2 \in R_+ \times R_+:$

$$\lim_{\substack{\delta_1 \rightarrow 0 \\ \delta_2 \rightarrow 0}} \varphi(\delta_1, \delta_2; \eta_1, \eta_2) = 0;$$

4. $\varphi(\delta_1, \delta_2; 2\eta_1, 2\eta_2) \leq \varphi(\delta_1, \delta_2; \eta_1, \eta_2)$ bu erda “ \leq ” munasabatdagi o'zgarmlar $\delta_1, \delta_2; \eta_1, \eta_2$ larga bog'liq emas.

E nuqtali to'plam, $z_0 \in E, \varphi \in Q$ bo'lsin. U holda quyidagi funksiyalar snfini kiritamiz:

$$H_{\varphi, E}^{z_0} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{f \in C(E): \omega_f^{t_0}(\delta_1, \delta_2; \eta_1, \eta_2) \leq C_f \varphi(\delta_1, \delta_2; \eta_1, \eta_2)\}, (\delta_i > 0, \eta_i > 0, i = 1, 2).$$

Ikki o'zgaruvchili funksiyaning lokal uzluksizlik moduli orqali $H_{\mu, \nu}^{\alpha+\beta, \lambda+\gamma}$ va $D_{\mu, \nu}^{\beta, \gamma}$ funksiyalar sinflarini quyidagich ifodalash mumkin:

$$f \in H_{\mu, \nu}^{\alpha+\beta, \lambda+\gamma} \Leftrightarrow \omega_f^{t_0}(\delta_1, \delta_2; \eta_1, \eta_2) = O(\min\{\delta_1^\alpha, \eta_1^{\alpha+\beta}\}, \min\{\delta_2^\gamma, \eta_2^{\lambda+\gamma}\}),$$

$$\forall \delta_i, \eta_i (i = 1, 2): 0 < \frac{\delta_i}{2} \leq \eta_i \leq \pi,$$

$$f \in D_{\mu, \nu}^{\beta, \gamma} \Leftrightarrow \omega_f^{t_0}(\delta_1, \delta_2; \eta_1, \eta_2) = O(\delta_1^\mu \cdot \eta_1^\beta \cdot \delta_2^\nu \cdot \eta_2^\gamma), \forall \delta_i, \eta_i (i = 1, 2): 0 < \frac{\delta_i}{2} \leq \eta_i \leq \pi.$$

Agar ikki o'zgaruvchili $f(x, y)$ funksiyaning bir argument ozgarmas bo'lsa, u holda bu funksiyaning lokal uzluksizlik moduli bir o'zgaruvchili funksiyaning lokal uzluksizlik moduli bilan ustma-ust tushadi, ya'ni, masalan $y = \text{const}$ bo'lganda

$$\omega_f^{z_0}(\delta_1, \delta_2; \eta_1, \eta_2) = \omega_f^{z_0}(\delta, \eta).$$

$H_{\mu, \nu}^{\alpha+\beta, \lambda+\gamma}$ va $D_{\mu, \nu}^{\beta, \gamma}$ funksiyalar sinfi uchun quyidagi munosabat o'rinli:

$$D_{\mu, \nu}^{\beta, \gamma}((x_0, y_0), [0, 2\pi] \times [0, 2\pi]) \subset H_{\mu, \nu}^{\alpha+\beta, \lambda+\gamma}((x_0, y_0), [0, 2\pi] \times [0, 2\pi]).$$

Masalan, ikki o'zgaruvchili funksiyalar uchun A.A.Gonchar masalasini quyidagicha qo'yish mumkin: *agar $f \in H_{\mu, \nu}^{\alpha+\beta, \lambda+\gamma}((x_0, y_0), [0, 2\pi] \times [0, 2\pi])$ bo'lsa, u holda z_0 nuqta atrofida*

$$\tilde{f}(x, y) = - \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} f(t, \tau) \text{ctg} \frac{t-x}{2} \text{ctg} \frac{\tau-y}{2} dt d\tau$$

maxsus integral o'zini qanday tutishini aniqlang?

Bu erda maxsus integral Koshining bosh qiymati ma'nosida tushiniladi.

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